

Magnetite biomineralization in *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense*: a time-resolved X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy study

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Abstract

Magnetotactic bacteria biosynthesize high quality magnetite nanoparticles that allow them to orientate in the geomagnetic field. In this work we have followed the process of biomineralization of these magnetite nanoparticles. We have performed a time-resolved study on

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magnetotactic bacteria *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense* strain MSR-1. From the combination of magnetic and structural studies by means of Fe K-edge X-ray Absorption Near Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) and High-Resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM) we have identified and quantified two phases of Fe (ferrihydrite and magnetite) involved in the biomineralization process, confirming the role of ferrihydrite as the source of Fe ions for magnetite biomineralization in *M. gryphiswaldense*. We have distinguished two steps in the biomineralization process: the first, in which Fe is accumulated in the form of ferrihydrite, and the second, in which the magnetite is rapidly biomineralized from ferrihydrite. The origin of the ferrihydrite could be at bacterial ferritin cores, as suggested by their similar structure.

Nature is a school for materials science and its associated disciplines such as Chemistry and Physics due to the ability to design crystalline structures whose properties are often superior to those of similar synthetic materials. The biologically controlled formation of inorganic compounds is called biomineralization. This process occurs in all organisms, from bacteria to humans. In particular, iron can be biomineralized in Fe(III) oxyhydroxide phase, ferrihydrite, by an iron storage protein, the ferritin. Some organisms biomineralize other iron oxides like goethite, α -FeOOH (limpets), lepidocrocite, γ -FeOOH (chiton)¹ and, the most common, magnetite, Fe₃O₄, that has been found in magnetotactic bacteria² and vertebrates such as pigeons, salmon, trouts (see [3] and references therein) and even humans.⁴ In the latter, the appearance of magnetite has been associated to some degenerative diseases such as Parkinson's and Alzheimer's diseases.⁵

In the particular case of magnetotactic bacteria, they are able to mineralize magnetite nanocrystals with high chemical purity, species-specific crystal morphology on shape and size and narrow size distribution. The magnetic nanoparticle is surrounded by a lipid bilayer with proteins, about 3-4 nm thick, and the nanoparticle together with this membrane is called magnetosome. The magnetotactic bacteria exert a highly precise biological control that determines the size, shape, and properties of the magnetite particles. These bacteria use these magnetosomes, which are organized in chains, as a compass needle that allows the bacteria to align in and navigate along the geomagnetic field lines.⁶

Although magnetotactic bacteria were first observed in 1963 by Bellini in Italy⁷ and were introduced to the worldwide scientific community in 1975 by Blakemore,² the interest on them has reappeared in the last years because of the potential biomedical applications of the magnetosomes.⁸⁻¹¹

A good understanding of the biomineralization process is the key for addressing challenges as the design of new materials. In general, little is known about the biomineralization process of the bacteria, but several steps have been identified:⁶ (i) magnetosome vesicles are formed,¹² (ii) iron is uptaken from the environment, (iii) iron is transported into the magnetosome vesicle, and finally (iv) iron is nucleated and precipitated in the form of magnetite.

Different models have been proposed regarding this last step. First, by means of Mössbauer spectroscopy and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), Frankel *et al.*¹³ suggest that magnetite is formed from a ferrihydrite precursor, which in a later work¹⁴ is suggested to be localized at the shell of the magnetite nanoparticles. On the other hand, Faivre *et al.*,¹⁵ using the same techniques in a time-resolved study, do not find evidence of the existence of a mineral precursor, and suggest as a possible mechanism of magnetite biomineralization a fast coprecipitation of Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺ ions within the magnetosome vesicle, a hypothesis that was proposed earlier by Arakaki *et al.*¹⁶ These Fe ions would be predominantly located at the cellular membrane in the form of a ferrous high-spin species and into a ferritin-like protein.¹⁵ The role of ferrihydrite as a source of Fe for magnetite biomineralization has also been suggested by Watanabe *et al.*¹⁷ by means of Raman spectroscopy. A different mechanism is proposed by Staniland *et al.*¹⁸ In this work, by means of X-ray Absorption spectroscopy and X-ray Magnetic Circular Dichroism on the soft Fe L_{2,3}-edges, they found a shell of a non-magnetic Fe oxide, hematite (α -Fe₂O₃), around the magnetite particles, which they suggest acts as the precursor of magnetite.

In the present work, we study the biomineralization process of the magnetotactic bacteria *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense* strain MSR-1 by the combination of magnetic and structural techniques in a time-resolved study. These techniques allow identifying two Fe phases during the process (magnetite and ferrihydrite) and, more importantly, allow obtaining quantitative results

on the mass of each phase all along the process. Besides more commonly used techniques like Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES), magnetic analysis, and Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), we have performed Fe K-edge X-ray Absorption Near Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) and High-resolution Transmission Electron Microscopy (HRTEM).

The advantage of the latter techniques with respect to those used in previous works, especially Mössbauer spectroscopy and soft X-ray Absorption Spectroscopy, is important. XANES is an element specific technique, sensitive to the oxidation state and to the local structure of the absorber element, in our case the Fe atom. Using hard X-rays at the Fe K-edge, instead of soft X-rays as in [18], allows us to work with the whole cell, avoiding the process of extraction of magnetosomes. Additionally, this technique is a powerful tool not only to identify but also quantify the different Fe inorganic phases present in the cell regardless of their magnetic state, which can be very complex and may mask magnetically weak phases as in Mössbauer spectroscopy or X-ray Magnetic Circular Dichroism.

Results and discussion

Figure 1 shows a TEM image of *M. gryphiswaldense* with a fully-formed magnetosome chain obtained after 72 h (4320 min) of incubation in a medium containing Fe(III)-citrate. *M. gryphiswaldense* synthesizes cubo-octahedral magnetite particles with an average diameter of 40 nm and narrow size distribution (Figure 1a). The mean number of magnetosomes per cell ranges between 20 and 25, which, assuming a mean particle size of 45 nm and a density of magnetite of $5.2 \cdot 10^3 \text{ kg/m}^3$, gives, in a first estimation, a mass of 3.5 to 4.3 fg of magnetite per cell. Electron micro-diffraction on a single particle confirms that the magnetosomes are single crystals with a diffraction pattern that corresponds to magnetite (Figure 1b). The magnetic response of the cells does also correspond to pure magnetite, as confirmed by the evolution of the magnetization as a function of temperature measured at 5 mT (Figure 2), which shows a sharp feature at 107 K that is due to the Verwey transition, a well-known characteristic of pure magnetite.¹⁹ The presence of this sharp transition

temperature together with the perfect electron micro-diffraction patterns for the biogenic magnetite are a clear indication of the high quality of the crystals obtained from the biomineralization process.

Figure 1: a) TEM image of *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense* after 4320 min (72 h) of incubation in a medium containing Fe(III)-citrate. The chain of magnetosomes can be clearly observed. b) Size distribution histogram and c) micro-diffraction pattern of a single magnetosome.

In order to follow the early stages of the biomineralization process of the bacteria, non-magnetic cells ($t = 0$) were obtained after 5 passages in an iron-free medium, incubated under aerobic conditions.

In order to induce the magnetite biomineralization, iron-starved cultures in mid-logarithmic growth phase were harvested by centrifugation and the cells were transferred to fresh medium supplemented with 100 μ M Fe(III)-citrate. At specified time intervals from $t = 20$ to 360 min, the cells were collected and fixed in 2% formaldehyde for Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) imaging, Atomic Emission Spectroscopy ICP-AES, magnetic characterization, X-ray Absorption Near Edge Spectroscopy (XANES) and High Resolution TEM (HRTEM). The bacterial growth and the magnetic response were monitored by an optical density method (see Figure 8 in the Supporting Information).

The mass of iron uptaken by the cells during the biomineralization process as determined by ICP-AES and normalized to the total number of cells is shown in table 1. According to these

Figure 2: Magnetization versus temperature measured at 5 mT of *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense* after 4320 min (72 h) of incubation in a medium containing Fe(III)-citrate. The arrow marks the Verwey transition, characteristic of magnetite.

measurements, the mass of Fe per cell increases during the biomineralization process from 0.4 $\text{fg}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{cell}$ at the beginning of the process up to 2.3 $\text{fg}_{\text{Fe}}/\text{cell}$ at the end, thus the mass of Fe per cell increases by a factor of 5. As will be shown in the following, XANES and magnetic measurements show that the Fe uptaken by the cells is distributed in two Fe compounds: magnetite and ferrihydrite.

Table 1: Mass of Fe per cell as obtained by ICP-AES at every time after Fe induction, and mean particle size ($\langle D \rangle$) and distribution width (σ) as obtained from TEM imaging (Figure 3).

t (min)	20	60	100	140	180	240	360
mass of Fe (fg/cell)	0.4(1)	0.6(1)	0.3(1)	0.6(1)	1.0(2)	1.8(3)	2.3(3)
$\langle D \rangle$ (nm)	22.4	26.0	22.0	25.8	27.9	26	31.2
σ (nm)	6.6	10.5	7.7	8.3	9.6	8	11.6

TEM images of the bacteria at each time after Fe induction allow following the magnetosomes formation process and how they arrange in chains. In Figure 3 we present some TEM images with the corresponding size-distribution histograms that underline the main features found during the biomineralization process. The mean diameter ($\langle D \rangle$) and distribution width (σ) extracted from the histograms is presented in table 1. As shown in Figure 3, at increasing times after Fe induction,

the number and size of the nanoparticles increases. At early stages, $t = 0 - 60$ min, most of the bacteria do not present nanoparticles, and only occasionally some isolated nanoparticles can be observed. As the time after Fe induction increases, the number of bacteria with nanoparticles does also increase. Most of these nanoparticles are isolated, but from $t = 100$ min, they organize in small "subchains" containing around 3 – 6 nanoparticles. With increasing time, these "subchains" become more frequent and closer together, and the size of the nanoparticles steadily increases. From $t = 240$ min, some long chains of several nanoparticles (> 6) are formed by the union of these small "subchains". From there on, the chains become longer, and formed by better defined and increasingly bigger nanoparticles.

Figure 3: Time-resolved magnetosome formation followed by TEM together with the corresponding size-distribution histograms. The mean diameter ($\langle D \rangle$) and distribution width (σ) extracted from the histograms are presented in table 1.

Bacteria at every time after Fe induction have been characterized magnetically by measuring their room-temperature hysteresis loops. As will be shown in the following, this analysis has allowed us to assess how the mass of magnetite increases with the time after Fe induction and also to quantify the mass of magnetite per cell. This is because the ferrimagnetic signal of magnetite

is much larger than any other in the samples and easily reaches magnetic saturation. On the other hand, the other magnetic signals present in the samples evolve linearly with the applied field at room temperature (diamagnetic signal from the organic parts and antiferromagnetic or weakly superparamagnetic from the ferrihydrite phase that will be analyzed further in the next paragraphs) and can be easily subtracted from the experimental data.

The hysteresis loops at every t are shown in Figure 4 after subtraction of the linear magnetic contribution mentioned above. From the saturation magnetization of the loop, M_s , and the number of cells per sample, we have estimated the mass of magnetite per cell, taken into account that M_s for bulk magnetite is $92 \text{ Am}^2/\text{kg}$. The results show that at the first stages of the biomineralization process $t \leq 100$ min, the mass of magnetite per cell is very small, $0.2 \pm 0.1 \text{ fg}_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}/\text{cell}$, but increases quickly up to $2.9 \pm 0.1 \text{ fg}_{\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4}/\text{cell}$ for $t = 360$ min. This value is still lower than the mass of magnetite estimated previously for bacteria with fully-formed magnetosome chains (3.5 to 4.3 fg/cell), indicating that the biomineralization process is not yet complete at 360 min. At this point, it should be noted that even though magneto-optical density on the cultivates at $t = 0$ and $t = 20$ min is zero ($C_{\text{mag}} = 0$) (see Figure 8 in the Supporting Information), magnetic measurements by means of room-temperature hysteresis loops reveal a barely measurable magnetic signal, an indication of the presence of a few isolated magnetite particles as shown previously in the TEM images.

Additionally, at low magnetic field values, the hysteresis loops present a butterfly shape that disappears at $t \geq 240$ min. The origin of this butterfly shape is attributed to the coexistence of superparamagnetic and ferrimagnetic magnetite nanoparticles. In fact, the contribution of smaller (superparamagnetic) magnetite nanoparticles is important at the first stages of the biomineralization process, but this contribution is masked by the prevalence of bigger (ferrimagnetic) particles at later stages of the process.

In order to identify the different Fe phases present in the bacteria at every time after Fe induction, we have performed Fe K-edge X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES) experiments at the XAFS beamline of the Elettra Synchrotron (Italy).

Figure 5 shows an evolution of the XANES spectra during the biomineralization process at

Figure 4: Hysteresis loops (after removal of the linear magnetic contribution) measured at room temperature at every t after Fe induction. In the inset the shape of the hysteresis loop at low fields is depicted.

energies below the edge, at the edge (7112 eV) and above the edge.

At early stages of the biomineralization process, the Fe K-edge XANES spectra show a shoulder, at around 14 eV below the edge, that transforms into a well-defined peak at the last stages of the biomineralization process. This pre-edge peak corresponds to a $1s$ to $3d$ transition, forbidden by the dipole selection rules. The intensity and width of this peak is sensitive to the symmetry around the absorbing atom.²⁰ The change of the pre-edge peak with the time elapsed after Fe induction reflects a change on the symmetry around the Fe atoms, from a centrosymmetric (broad and low in intensity pre-edge peak) to a non-centrosymmetric site (narrow and more intense pre-edge peak).

The edge position is a clear-cut indication of the oxidation state of the absorbing atom, Fe in this case. In fact, we have checked that the edge position displaces 7 eV to lower energies when the oxidation state decreases from Fe^{3+} , measured for reference compounds $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (maghemite) and Fe(III)-citrate, to Fe^{2+} , measured for the reference compound FeO (Figure 9 in the Supporting Information). The edge position of the first bacterial sample, $t = 20$ min, is coincident with a pure Fe^{3+} compound. As the biomineralization process evolves, the energy of the absorption edge

Figure 5: a) Normalized XANES spectra at Fe K-edge obtained for the samples at every time after Fe induction. b) The pre-edge region in a more-detailed depiction.

displaces ~ 2 eV to lower energies, indicating that the Fe is reducing as the process evolves, from Fe^{3+} to the presence of both Fe^{3+} , Fe^{2+} oxidation states whose relative amount changes with the time elapsed after Fe induction. It is well known that magnetite (Fe_3O_4) is an inverse spinel in which 8 Fe^{3+} occupy the noncentrosymmetric tetrahedral sites and 8 Fe^{2+} and 8 Fe^{3+} occupy the centrosymmetric octahedral sites. Therefore, both features, the appearance of the pre-edge peak and the shift of the edge position, are evidences of the magnetite being formed from a pure Fe^{3+} compound.

Finally, above the edge, the XANES spectra evolve progressively with increasing time after Fe induction. The main feature is the evolution of a shoulder observed at ~ 7136 eV that disappears as the process goes on. The evolution of the oscillations above the edge indicates that the surroundings of the Fe atoms change during the biomineralization process.

In order to obtain quantitative information on the different phases present in the cells and their evolution with the time elapsed after Fe induction, the normalized spectra were fitted to a linear combination of two reference compounds. The percentage of each phase is the atomic fraction of the two phases present in the sample.

The first reference compound is the bacteria at $t = 20$ min, which according to previous TEM and magnetic measurements is essentially free of magnetite. In fact, as noted before, the edge position of this spectrum corresponds to a pure Fe^{3+} compound, and comparing this spectrum with those of Fe^{3+} inorganic compounds such as hematite ($\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), maghemite ($\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$), goethite ($\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$), Fe(III)-citrate, lepidocrocite ($\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$) and ferrihydrite, we found that it can be clearly identified as a ferrihydrite-like structure (Figure 10 in the Supporting Information). However, the bacterial spectrum presents a shoulder at ~ 7136 eV that is not present in the ferrihydrite spectrum. This shoulder appears in ferrihydrite cores of ferritin proteins with high phosphorous content,²¹ which in fact is the case in bacterial ferritin proteins.²² Due to these special features of biogenic ferrihydrite from bacteria as compared to inorganic ferrihydrite, the spectrum of the bacteria at $t = 20$ min was chosen as a reference compound for biogenic ferrihydrite for the rest of the samples. However, it should be noted that even though there is a small quantity of magnetite in

these bacteria at $t = 20$ min, introducing magnetite in the XANES fit does not improve its quality. Moreover, introducing up to a 10% of magnetite in the fit does only shift the edge position by 0.2 eV, which is below the resolution limit of our XANES measurements (0.3 eV).

The second reference compound corresponds to the bacteria with fully-formed magnetosome chains ($t = 4320$ min (72 hours)). Comparing this spectrum with the one of bulk magnetite it can be readily seen that both are identical (Figure 10 of the Supporting Information). However, a 10% of ferrihydrite cannot be discarded owing to the resolution limit of the experiment, as noted before.

The spectra of the bacteria at every time after Fe induction were then fitted to a linear combination of both biogenic references, ferrihydrite ($t = 20$ min) and magnetite ($t = 4320$ min (72 hours)). As a result of these fits we have been able to quantify the atomic fraction of ferrihydrite and magnetite at each time after Fe induction, as shown in Table 2. From these data it can be readily seen that at the beginning of the biomineralization process mostly ferrihydrite is present in the cells, which transforms progressively to magnetite as the process evolves.

Table 2: Atomic fraction of biogenic ferrihydrite (bacteria at $t = 20$ min) and biogenic magnetite ($t = 4320$ min (72 hours)) as obtained from the linear combination of XANES spectra at every t after Fe induction.

t (min)	20	60	100	140	180	240	360
Ferrihydrite	1.0(1)	0.6(1)	0.6(1)	0.5(1)	0.3(1)	0.2(1)	0.0(1)
Magnetite	0.0(1)	0.4(1)	0.4(1)	0.5(1)	0.7(1)	0.8(1)	1.0(1)

From the atomic fraction of biogenic ferrihydrite and magnetite as determined by XANES, and the mass of magnetite obtained from the saturation magnetization value M_s of the hysteresis loops, we have been able to determine the mass of ferrihydrite in the cells (see the Experimental section) and to calculate the total mass of Fe per cell. The agreement of these values with the ones obtained from ICP-AES is very good, as observed in Figure 6a, which supports the reliability of the results.

Furthermore, in Figure 6b we have represented the mass of Fe per cell in the form of both ferrihydrite and magnetite at each time after Fe induction. These results show that the biomineralization process takes place in two steps. Firstly, up to $t = 140$ min, the process of magnetite biomineralization is slow and the mass of ferrihydrite per cell remains practically constant, suggesting that in

these stages the accumulation of Fe in the form of ferrihydrite prevails over the biomineralization of magnetite. Secondly, after $t = 140$ min, the biomineralization process of magnetite becomes faster and the mass of ferrihydrite decreases. This suggests that ferrihydrite is progressively being transformed into magnetite but is not being replaced, as suggested by the negligible amount of ferrihydrite at $t = 360$.

Figure 6: a) Mass of Fe per cell as determined by ICP-AES (table 1) and by a combination of XANES and magnetic measurements (MH). The line is a guide for the eye. b) Distribution of the mass of Fe per cell in the ferrihydrite and magnetite phases as determined by the combination of magnetic and XANES results.

The question arising at this point is in which cellular compartment the bacteria store the ferrihydrite they use as a source of Fe and which, according to XANES results, is likely to be forming the cores of bacterial ferritin proteins.

In order to shed light on this matter, we have performed high resolution TEM experiments using an TITAN3 (FEI) microscope at the Instituto de Nanociencia de Aragón (Spain). These experiments were performed on horse spleen ferritin as a reference for biogenic ferrihydrite and

on the bacterial sample at $t = 20$ min after Fe induction, in which, according to our previous results, the Fe is mainly forming ferrihydrite.

As expected for ferrihydrite cores from horse spleen ferritin, HRTEM shows poorly crystallized nanoparticles of around 5 nm in size (Figure 7a). On the other hand, HRTEM images of bacteria at $t = 20$ min show very few isolated particles, always larger than 9 nm in size (see Figure 7b), crystallized in the magnetite (Fe_3O_4) phase. The crystalline structure has been determined from the indexation of the diffraction spots (see the inset of Figure 7b), which yields a magnetite structure oriented in the $[2,1,1]$ zone axis.

Therefore, HRTEM observations did not reveal the presence of ferrihydrite in the samples. However, it should be noted that ferrihydrite cores from bacterial ferritin proteins are less dense than mammalian ferritins because of their larger phosphorous content.²² These cores have then a lower degree of crystallinity than mammalian ferritins and therefore present a very poor diffraction contrast in HRTEM, which could explain why we have not been able to image them.

Figure 7: HRTEM image of commercial horse spleen ferritin (a) and of an isolated nanoparticle from the $t = 20$ min bacterial sample (b). The insets show the Fast Fourier Transform of one of the ferritin nanoparticles (a), and the diffractogram of the magnetite nanoparticle inside the bacteria (b).

In conclusion, we have performed a time-resolved study on the biomineralization process of the

magnetotactic bacteria *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense* strain MSR-1 combining structural and magnetic techniques. XANES allows identifying two Fe phases present in the bacteria: ferrihydrite with a similar structure as that of bacterial ferritin cores, and magnetite. This confirms the role of ferrihydrite as a source of Fe for the magnetite biomineralization. Additionally, we have been able to quantify the mass of each phase at every time after Fe induction, distinguishing two steps in the biomineralization process: the first, in which Fe is accumulated in the form of ferrihydrite, and the second, in which the magnetite is rapidly biomineralized from ferrihydrite. HRTEM confirms that even the smallest and not fully grown particles observed, of ≈ 9 nm, are pure crystalline magnetite and rule out the existence of a core-shell structure as suggested elsewhere.¹³ The yet unanswered question is the cell-compartment in which the bacteria store the ferrihydrite.

Experimental

Bacterial strain and growth conditions

The bacteria studied in this work were *Magnetospirillum gryphiswaldense* strain MSR-1 (DMSZ 6631). *M. gryphiswaldense* was cultured in a flask standard medium (FSM) described by Heyen & Schüler²³ (per litre of deionized water: 0.1 g KH_2PO_4 , 0.15 g $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 2.38 g Hepes, 0.34 g NaNO_3 , 0.1 g yeast extract, 3 g soy bean peptone). The medium contained 0.3% (wt/vol) sodium pyruvate as a carbon source. When needed, Fe(III)-citrate was added at a final concentration of 100 μM . Cells were grown at 28°C without agitation in loosely stoppered bottles with a headspace-to-liquid ratio of approximately 1:4 and air was used in the headspace. An inoculum of 10% of the culture volume was used. Microaerobic conditions arose in the medium at higher cell densities by oxygen consumption of cells. Bacterial growth and magnetic response of the cells were monitored turbidimetrically at 565 nm (OD_{565}). For the magneto-optical density measurements, C_{mag} , two bar magnets (neodymium iron boron) were placed into the sample holder to create a magnetic field ($\mu_0 H = 20$ mT) parallel and perpendicularly to the incident light beam. The ratio of the resulting maximum and minimum OD values minus 1 ($C_{\text{mag}} = (\text{OD}_{\parallel} / \text{OD}_{\perp}) - 1$) can be used as a rapid

qualitative estimation of magnetite formation. Thus, $C_{\text{mag}} = 0$ was obtained for non-magnetic cells; this value increases with increasing magnetosomes and chain formation.²⁴

Time-course experiments

In order to follow the early stages of magnetite synthesis, non-magnetic cells were obtained after 4 or 5 passages in a free iron medium incubated under aerobic conditions (shaking at 170 rpm). For induction of magnetite biomineralization, iron starved cells in mid-logarithmic growth phase were harvested by centrifugation and transferred to fresh medium supplemented with 100 μM Fe(III)-citrate. Culture was carried out at 28°C under microaerobic conditions (without agitation). At specified time intervals, samples were collected and fixed in 2% formaldehyde for subsequent analysis.

The number of bacteria at each time after Fe induction was determined by the standard acridine orange procedure. Bacteria were retained on 0.22 micron pore-size black polycarbonate filters and examined under epifluorescence microscopy.

The mass of Fe uptaken by the cells was determined by Inductively Coupled Plasma Atomic Emission Spectrometry (ICP-AES). The samples were centrifuged (6000 rpm - 20 min) and the supernatants were decanted, acidified to pH 2-3 with nitric acid and analyzed directly. The iron uptaken by the cell at each time after Fe induction, t , was determined by subtraction of the iron in the supernatant at $t = 0$ and the one obtained at time t .

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) and High-resolution TEM (HRTEM)

Electron microscopy was performed on unstained cells adsorbed onto 300 mesh carbon-coated copper grids.

Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM) images were obtained with a Philips EM208S electron microscope at an accelerating voltage of 70 kV. The particle size distribution was analyzed using standard software for digital electron microscope image processing, ImageJ.²⁵ Electron microdiffraction was performed on a Philips CM200 electron microscope at an accelerating voltage of

200 kV and with an electron beam size of 40 nm.

High-resolution TEM (HRTEM) images were taken at a TITAN3 (FEI) microscope, working at 300 kV. This Ultra High Resolution microscope is equipped with a SuperTwin objective lens and a CETCOR Cs-objective corrector from CEOS Company allowing a point to point resolution of 0.08 nm. Correction of the spherical aberration of the objective lens improves significantly the spatial resolution of the HRTEM images.

Magnetic characterization

The room temperature hysteresis loops of the samples of the time-resolved experiment were measured using a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM) up to a maximum applied field of 1 T. For these measurements cells were collected by centrifugation at 4°C 6000 rpm for 15 minutes. The obtained pellets were then washed three times with 10 mM HEPES, pH 7.4 and in this shape were measured in the VSM.

The magnetic characterization of bacteria with fully-formed magnetosome chains ($t = 4320$ min (72 hours)) was carried out in a SQUID magnetometer. Bacterial pellets were left to dry at 37°C before the SQUID measurement.

X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES). Experiment and sample preparation

For the X-ray Absorption Fine Structure Spectroscopy (XANES) experiments the same pellets used for the magnetic characterization were deposited onto Kapton foil and left to dry at 37°C. The Kapton foil had been adhered to a sample holder specially designed to concentrate the sample in thin disks of ~ 28 mm².

XANES measurements were performed at the Elettra Synchrotron in Trieste, Italy. Room temperature Fe K-edge XANES spectra of bacteria at every t after Fe induction were recorded simultaneously in transmission and fluorescence mode with a single-element solid-state detector. For the

subsequent analysis, the fluorescence spectra were used for the samples with low Fe contents, but for higher Fe contents where auto-absorption mechanisms were important, the transmission spectra were used. In order to improve the data reliability, at least three spectra were recorded for each sample.

The monochromator used in the experiments was a double crystal of Si(111). The energy edge of each bacterial sample was carefully calibrated by recording simultaneously a XANES spectrum of a Fe foil using the transmitted intensity of the sample. In these conditions, the edge position of the sample can be determined with an accuracy of 0.3 eV.

XANES spectra of bacteria at every time after Fe induction were measured up to $k = 9 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ and up to $k = 16 \text{ \AA}^{-1}$ for the bacteria at $t = 4320 \text{ min}$ (72 hours).

Additionally, XANES spectra of mature bacteria and standard Fe oxides (Fe_3O_4 (magnetite), FeO , $\alpha\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (hematite), $\gamma\text{-Fe}_2\text{O}_3$ (maghemite), Fe(III)-citrate) and hydro-oxides ($\alpha\text{-FeOOH}$ (goethite), $\gamma\text{-FeOOH}$ (lepidocrocite)) were measured in transmission configuration for comparison.

X-ray Absorption Near Edge Structure (XANES). Data Analysis

The experimental spectra were normalized using standard procedures for background subtraction and data normalization.²⁶ The normalized spectra of bacteria at every t were then fitted to a linear combination of normalized spectra of the reference compounds:

$$\alpha \times \text{bacterial magnetite } (t = 4320 \text{ min}) + (1 - \alpha) \times \text{bacterial ferrihydrite } (t = 20 \text{ min}), \quad (1)$$

where α (with the constraint $\alpha \leq 1$) directly quantifies the atomic fraction of each phase in the samples. The refinement has been performed minimizing the square residual in which the sum runs over the experimental points: $\chi^2 = \sum_i (\mu_i^{\text{exp}} - \mu_i^{\text{theo}})^2$, where μ^{exp} and μ^{theo} are the experimental and fitted data, respectively.

In order to estimate the mass of Fe in the ferrihydrite phase and therefore the total mass of

Fe per cell, we have used the relative atomic proportions of Fe atoms forming magnetite and ferrihydrite as obtained from the linear combination fits of the corresponding XANES spectra, together with the mass of Fe in the magnetite phase as obtained from the M_s of the hysteresis loops:

$$m_{\text{Fe}}(\text{ferrihydrite}) = \frac{1 - \alpha}{\alpha} m_{\text{Fe}}(\text{magnetite}) \quad (2)$$

where $m_{\text{Fe}}(\text{ferrihydrite})$ and $m_{\text{Fe}}(\text{magnetite})$ are the mass fraction of Fe in the ferrihydrite phase and in the magnetite phase, respectively.

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Supporting Information Available

Figure 8: Optical density (OD), and ($C_{\text{mag}} = (OD_{\parallel}/OD_{\perp}) - 1$), as a function of the time after Fe induction.

Figure 9: XANES spectra of several Fe compounds in order to underline the shift to lower energies of the absorption edge when reducing from Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} .

This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org/>.

Figure 10: Comparison of the XANES spectra of: a) bacteria at $t = 20$ min after Fe induction and inorganic ferrihydrite; b) bacteria at $t = 4320$ min (72 hours) and inorganic magnetite.

Figure 11: XANES spectra and their corresponding fits for the bacteria obtained at every time after Fe induction. In the bottom, the residual of the fits is shown.

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Graphical TOC Entry

